

Convention and Visitors Bureaus as Catalysts for MICE Tourism: The Case of Oman

Maram Yaqoob Said Al Sarkhi¹, Jayashree Krishnamurthy², Mohammed Al Jabri³

^{1,2}Oman Tourism College, Muscat, Sultanate of Oman

³Ministry of Heritage & Tourism, Muscat, Sultanate of Oman

Email: maramyaqoopalsarkhi@gmail.com; Jayashree.krishnamurthy@otc.edu.om; mjabri@mht.gov.om

Citation: Al Sarkhi, M. Y. S., Krishnamurthy, J. & Al Jabri, M. (2025). Analysis of the Role of Convention and Visitors Bureaus in Marketing of Destinations for Convention Tourism: Case Study Oman. *International Journal of Research in Entrepreneurship & Business Studies*, 6(3), 1-20.
<https://doi.org/10.47259/ijrebs.2025.631>

Received on 27th Apr. 2025
Revised on 14th May. 2025
Accepted on 12th Jun. 2025
Published on 11th Jul. 2025

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Abstract

Purpose: The aim of the study was to understand the role and significance of Convention and Visitors Bureaus (CVBs) in supporting and promoting global conference, exhibition, and convention tourism, and to analyse the specific role of the OCB in enhancing Oman's presence within the international MICE tourism sector.

Design/methodology/approach: A qualitative research approach was utilized to explore the experiences, challenges, and strategies of stakeholders involved in the development and promotion of MICE tourism in Oman. The population included the Oman Convention Bureau and all stakeholders, including hotels and event planners. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants. Primary data was collected through 10 semi-structured interviews, including government officials, event organizers, hotel managers, and representatives of major conference venues. All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analysed thematically to identify patterns and recurring trends. Data analysis was carried out using voice memos and manual coding to enhance the depth and validity of interpretations.

Findings: Stakeholders recognized Oman's cultural appeal, natural landscapes, and high-quality hospitality as key strengths but highlighted persistent challenges, including limited flight connectivity, visa delays, seasonal capacity gaps, and infrastructure constraints. While OCB's logistical support, visa facilitation, and international promotional campaigns were appreciated, concerns were raised about limited internal outreach, resource constraints, and over-reliance on the Oman Convention and Exhibition Centre (OCEC). Stakeholders emphasized the need for stronger digital platforms, coordinated engagement, streamlined visa processes, financial incentives, and diversified venues beyond Muscat. Technical shortcomings, such as disrupted Wi-Fi and payment issues, further underscored operational gaps. Calls were also made for improved transportation networks and closer alignment between public and private stakeholders.

Research Implications: Academically, the study contributes to the literature on conference and convention tourism by examining the evolving role of convention bureaus in emerging destinations, with a focus on Oman. Practically, it provides actionable insights for the OCB and its partners to refine strategies, address systemic challenges, and benchmark against global best practices. These improvements are critical to advancing Oman's Vision 2040 agenda for economic diversification and sustainable tourism growth.

Social Implications: Strengthening Oman's MICE industry through an empowered Convention Bureau fosters job creation, SME participation, and community engagement, while promoting cultural heritage and sustainable development. Enhanced collaboration ensures wider socio-economic benefits aligned with national priorities and Vision 2040.

Originality / Value: This study uniquely examines the Oman Convention Bureau's hybrid governance model, stakeholder dynamics, and competitive positioning, offering tailored recommendations to enhance Oman's MICE sector in alignment with Vision 2040—an area with limited prior academic research.

Keywords: Oman Convention Bureau, MICE tourism, Oman Tourism, Destination marketing, Convention and Visitors Bureau.

JEL: L83, Z30, Z32

Introduction

Convention and Visitors Bureaus (CVBs) are central to the promotion, development, and management of destinations in the Meetings, Incentives, Conferences, and Exhibitions (MICE) sector. Functioning as strategic intermediaries, they link event organizers with local service providers, thereby positioning destinations as competitive hubs for business gatherings. Their role extends beyond simple promotion, encompassing logistical support, guidance on local regulations, venue coordination, and the design of customized packages that enrich both organizer and visitor experiences. Equally important, CVBs contribute to destination branding by highlighting a location's unique cultural, natural, and infrastructural strengths, which help differentiate it in a highly competitive global market (Ford & Peeper, 2008).

Globally, the structure and functioning of CVBs vary considerably depending on market dynamics and governance systems. In the United States, many CVBs receive substantial public funding, often from local tax revenues, enabling them to promote both leisure and business tourism extensively. European bureaus, by contrast, typically concentrate on business-related events, particularly association meetings and conferences, and are more dependent on government grants and subsidies. In the Asia-Pacific region, innovative public-private collaborations—such as those demonstrated by the [Singapore Tourism Board](#) (2023) – have proven effective in combining state support with private-sector expertise to implement aggressive marketing and promotional campaigns aimed at attracting major international events.

Within this global context, the Oman Convention Bureau (OCB) plays a strategic role in advancing Oman's ambitions to become a recognized MICE destination. Established under the Ministry of Heritage and Tourism, the OCB operates as a national-level institution dedicated to showcasing Oman's strengths in the global MICE industry. Unlike individual venue managers such as the Oman Convention and Exhibition Centre, the OCB adopts an integrated approach, promoting the nation's cultural heritage, natural beauty, and modern infrastructure as part of a unified brand. Its mandate is closely aligned with Oman Vision 2040, which identifies tourism as a cornerstone of economic diversification and sustainable development. Through collaborations with hotels, venues, transportation providers, and service suppliers, the OCB seeks to build a cohesive ecosystem that supports large-scale international events and positions Oman as a viable alternative to established regional MICE hubs.

Several international organizations provide definitions that illustrate the functional scope of CVBs. The World Tourism Organization ([UNEP & UN Tourism](#), 2005) identifies a CVB as a non-profit entity responsible for promoting and organizing conferences, exhibitions, and business events while serving as the intermediary between event planners and local providers. Similarly, the [Events Industry Council \(2024\)](#) defines CVBs as incorporated non-profit or government entities tasked with promoting economic development through tourism, offering site selection services, local resource guidance, and both pre- and post-convention support. The International Congress and Convention Association ([ICCA](#), 2023) describes CVBs as destination marketing bodies whose main objective is to increase the number of events and conferences hosted at a city, regional, or national level. Taken together, these definitions underscore the bureau's dual function as both a marketing agent and a coordinating body that bridges governments, service providers, and international event organizers.

The economic significance of MICE tourism is substantial. According to the World Travel & Tourism Council ([World Travel & Tourism Council](#), 2019), MICE activities accounted for 21.5% of total global travel expenditure, with business travellers also contributing to leisure-related spending, thereby stimulating hospitality, transportation, and entertainment sectors. In 2018, global travel and tourism contributed USD 8.8 trillion to the world economy, with MICE tourism playing a notable role. Projections by [Allied Market Research](#) (2024) suggest that the global MICE market will grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 15.2% between 2021 and 2031, reaching USD 2.1 trillion. Much of this growth is expected to come from the Middle East and Asia-Pacific, where destinations such as Dubai, Singapore, and China have made significant investments in world-class MICE infrastructure.

Historically, CVBs originated in the United States, with the first organized bureau established in Detroit in 1896 to attract trade exhibitions and business meetings. The model quickly spread across North America as cities recognized the economic benefits of hosting large-scale conventions (Ford & Peeper, 2008). By the mid-20th century, European cities such as London, Paris, and Vienna had adopted the bureau model, though their operations relied more on government support and professional associations rather than local taxation ([Rogers & Davidson](#), 2016). In the 1980s and 1990s, cities in the Asia-Pacific region—including Singapore,

Hong Kong, and Sydney—developed strong CVB structures that combined government initiatives with private-sector engagement, helping these destinations establish themselves as global leaders in the MICE sector (Getz, 2008; Morrison, 2023).

In the present day, CVBs remain indispensable to tourism development, generating significant economic contributions through their facilitation of international events. For instance, CVB-led activities in cities like Miami have been shown to generate multimillion-dollar economic impacts (Greater Miami Convention & Visitors Bureau, 2025). Post-pandemic, the role of CVBs has evolved further, with many adopting digital marketing tools, advanced analytics, and sustainability-driven strategies to maintain competitiveness (World Travel & Tourism Council, 2023). Hybrid and virtual event formats, accelerated by the pandemic, have also become a central part of CVB service offerings (Captioning Star, 2022). In addition, the growing emphasis on green initiatives and eco-friendly practices reflects a global shift toward sustainable tourism promotion (OECD, 2024).

As of 2024, there are approximately 5,126 CVBs in the United States alone (Rose, 2024), while Europe maintains collaborative networks such as the 29-member Strategic Alliance of National Convention Bureaux (SANCB). Globally, the number of bureaus is estimated to exceed 6,000, though no single consolidated registry exists (Rose, 2024). To remain competitive, CVBs must continually innovate, adapt to changing industry dynamics, and foster collaborative networks that maximize their destination’s appeal in an increasingly crowded global market.

Convention Bureaus in Oman

In Oman, the Oman Convention Bureau (OCB) serves as the primary national body for advancing the country’s MICE sector. Operating under the Ministry of Heritage and Tourism, the bureau’s activities are integrated with the objectives of Oman Vision 2040, which prioritizes tourism as a driver of sustainable economic growth (Ohio Association of Convention and Visitor Bureaus, 2025). The OCB functions as a neutral facilitator for planners, supporting bids, coordinating logistics, and acting as the central link between venues, suppliers, and government stakeholders.

A central element of the OCB’s mission is to promote Oman’s distinctive strengths—including its cultural heritage, renowned hospitality, and sustainability practices—as key competitive advantages in the international MICE arena (Fletcher et al., 2017). Infrastructure such as the Oman Convention and Exhibition Centre complements these efforts by providing state-of-the-art facilities capable of hosting large-scale international events. In this way, the OCB not only enhances Oman’s visibility on the global stage but also fosters knowledge exchange, professional networking, and economic development through business tourism (Ohio Association of Convention and Visitor Bureaus, 2025).

Current Role of OCB

Currently, the Oman Convention Bureau is tasked with positioning the Sultanate as an emerging and competitive MICE destination. To achieve this, it works closely with stakeholders across the hospitality, transport, and event management sectors, as well as government entities, to strengthen the national MICE ecosystem (Ministry of Heritage and Tourism, 2021). Through targeted promotional strategies and international partnerships, the OCB seeks to attract major conferences, exhibitions, and corporate meetings that contribute to Oman’s long-term economic diversification and reinforce its role as a hub for regional and global business events.

Figure 1. Role of OCB in the MICE industry
 Source: [Ministry of Heritage and Tourism](#) (2021)

Problem Statement

Oman is actively seeking to increase its revenue from tourism, recognizing MICE tourism as a particularly promising segment due to its high economic impact and potential for year-round activity. However, the country faces formidable competition from regional powerhouses such as Dubai, Saudi Arabia, and Qatar, which are already well-established players in the global convention market. These competing destinations benefit from larger investments, stronger infrastructure, and longer market presence, making them the preferred choice for international event organizers. Despite its rich cultural and natural assets, Oman continues to struggle to capture its fair share of the global MICE market. This research seeks to critically analyze the role of the Oman Convention Bureau in supporting and enhancing convention tourism, exploring its current strategies, identifying existing gaps, and offering actionable recommendations for strengthening its position as a competitive MICE destination.

Research Questions

1. What is the role and significance of Convention and Visitors Bureaus in supporting and promoting MICE tourism at the global level?
2. How does the Oman Convention Bureau contribute to promoting MICE tourism, and what specific strategies are implemented to attract international conventions and exhibitions?

Research Objectives

1. To comprehensively understand the role and significance of Convention and Visitors Bureaus in supporting and promoting global conference, exhibition, and convention tourism.
2. To analyze the specific role of the Oman Convention Bureau in enhancing Oman's presence within the international MICE tourism sector.

Review of Literature

The meetings, incentives, conferences, and exhibitions (MICE) sector has become one of the most dynamic areas of global tourism, playing a crucial role in destination branding, economic diversification, and knowledge exchange (Ford & Peeper, 2008; World Travel & Tourism Council, 2019). Within this sector, Convention and Visitors Bureaus (CVBs) have emerged as pivotal institutions, acting as intermediaries that connect local stakeholders, international associations, and event organizers. Their strategic roles span destination marketing, bid management, stakeholder coordination, and the development of competitive advantage through branding and service quality (Rogers & Davidson, 2016; Delaney, 2021).

Globally, CVBs are recognized as drivers of competitiveness in the MICE industry, primarily by enhancing destination image and positioning (Latuszek, 2021). Research emphasizes that competitiveness is contingent not only upon physical infrastructure but also on attributes such as professionalism, hospitality, and cultural uniqueness (An et al., 2021; Zazueta-Hernández et al., 2024). The growing body of literature also highlights the importance of collaboration between stakeholders—including hotels, airlines, convention centres, and local governments—in ensuring destination success (Yoon & Wang, 2023; Lekgau & Tichaawa, 2024).

The significance of stakeholder collaboration has become especially visible in the post-pandemic recovery of the MICE sector. Studies from South Africa and Asia demonstrate that integrated supply chain approaches and multi-stakeholder partnerships are essential in restoring trust and competitiveness in the industry (Lekgau & Tichaawa, 2024; UNWTO, 2017). In addition, emerging research stresses innovation and creative tourism as mechanisms through which destinations can differentiate themselves in a highly competitive market (Disimulacion, 2024).

In terms of venue selection, scholars have identified multiple event attributes that influence organizers' decisions, including accessibility, venue quality, technology adoption, and sustainability credentials (An et al., 2021; Sriraksa et al., 2021). The role of transportation and connectivity is particularly emphasized in Asian destinations, where air accessibility has been shown to directly influence competitiveness (Sriraksa et al., 2021).

From an economic perspective, MICE tourism is viewed as a high-value segment that contributes to national GDP through direct spending, trade promotion, and knowledge-based spillovers (OECD, 2020; Allied Market Research, 2024). ICCA reports underline the exponential growth of international association meetings, underscoring the need for destinations to strategically position themselves within the global marketplace.

The Sultanate of Oman has increasingly recognized the MICE industry as a key avenue for economic diversification, consistent with the broader objectives of Oman Vision 2040 ([Ministry of Heritage & Tourism, 2021](#)). The establishment of the Oman Convention Bureau (OCB) reflects a strategic initiative to align tourism growth with sustainable development goals while leveraging Oman’s unique cultural and environmental assets ([Ohio Association of Convention and Visitor Bureaus, 2025](#); [Fletcher et al., 2017](#)). The OCB functions as a neutral facilitator, assisting with international bids, promoting the nation’s image, and coordinating stakeholders across the sector. Supporting infrastructure, notably the Oman Convention & Exhibition Centre (OCEC), has been central to positioning Oman as a credible global MICE destination ([Oxford Business Group, 2018](#); [Prabhu, 2024](#)).

Several studies affirm Oman’s growing role in the MICE industry, citing its hospitality, cultural heritage, and sustainable tourism policies as distinctive competitive advantages ([Oxford Business Group, 2018](#); [Prabhu, 2024](#)). Yet, literature also reveals that Oman remains an emerging market, where sustained stakeholder integration, innovation, and global branding strategies are required to achieve parity with established MICE hubs in the Gulf and Asia.

Overall, the literature converges on three key themes: (i) CVBs serve as strategic facilitators in destination marketing and competitiveness; (ii) stakeholder collaboration and infrastructure development are fundamental to the success of MICE destinations; and (iii) Oman, through the OCB and OCEC, has made significant strides in positioning itself but still faces challenges in fully realizing its potential. This gap underscores the relevance of the present study, which examines the specific role of the Oman Convention Bureau in marketing the Sultanate as a competitive destination for convention tourism.

Conceptual Models of CVB Competitiveness

[Delaney \(2021\)](#) proposed a conceptual framework for assessing the competitiveness of convention bureaus, emphasizing four interrelated elements: a network of relationships, core resources, additional services, and trust and experience. The model suggests that the success of a convention bureau is largely determined by its ability to cultivate strong linkages with key stakeholders, such as government agencies, business leaders, academics, and destination service providers. Equally important are the bureau’s core resources, including the provision of destination information, venue referrals, registration support, accommodation booking, and promotional services. Additional services, such as financial subventions and assistance with visa applications, further enhance the bureau’s value proposition for international event organizers. Finally, the accumulated trust and professional experience of the bureau play a decisive role in ensuring long-term competitiveness. Together, these elements drive the overall success of convention bureaus, which in turn contribute directly to the success and competitiveness of the destination as a whole.

Figure 2. Conceptual Model for Convention Bureau Competitiveness
 Source: [Delaney \(2021\)](#)

Research Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative research approach to explore the experiences, challenges, and strategies of stakeholders involved in the development and promotion of MICE tourism in Oman. Primary data was collected through 10 semi-structured interviews with purposively selected participants, including government

officials, event organizers, hotel managers, and representatives of major conference venues. This method enables the collection of rich, detailed insights while ensuring the inclusion of information-rich cases relevant to the research focus (Palinkas et al., 201).

The interviews, guided by open-ended questions, address themes such as marketing strategies, infrastructure limitations, stakeholder collaboration, and policy effectiveness. All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and analysed thematically to identify patterns and recurring trends. Findings were systematically categorized and compared with international best practices in MICE tourism, ensuring both rigor and contextual relevance. Data analysis was carried out using voice memos and manual coding to enhance the depth and validity of interpretations.

Findings

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

		Frequency	%
Gender	Male	9	90.0
	Female	1	10.0
Residence	Muscat	10	100.0
Status	Working	10	100.0
Designation	Director	3	30.0
	Manager	2	20.0
	Event Manager	1	10.0
	R & D Specialist	1	10.0
	Secretary	1	10.0
	Representative	2	20.0
Industry classification	MICE	2	20.0
	Facility Mgt.	1	10.0
	Health Care Sector	1	10.0
	Hospitality Industry	3	30.0
	Telecom Industry	1	10.0
	Other sector	2	20.0

Table 2. Interview with the Hospitality industry

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How often do you collaborate with OCB in terms of securing conferences and exhibitions (MICE tourism)?	It is reported that they maintain regular collaboration with the Oman Convention Bureau, especially during major bidding phases for regional and international conferences. This partnership is crucial during the annual MICE calendar planning and major industry exhibitions like IMEX or ATM.
2	What marketing strategies from OCB have directly benefited your hotel in getting business events?	OCB's participation in international trade shows and its destination marketing campaigns have significantly enhanced Oman's visibility. Their joint promotional materials and co-branding opportunities have directly driven inquiries and bookings to the hotels.
3	What percentage of total hotel occupancy comes from bookings related to meetings, conferences, and exhibitions, and how has this data changed in recent years?	MICE-related bookings contribute approximately 20–25% of our total occupancy for the Shangri-La Hotel. While there was a dip during the pandemic, we've observed a steady rebound with hybrid events and regional conferences. Furthermore, the booking rate for MICE tourism at the JW Marriott Hotel reached 30-35% last year and is increasing to 45-53% this year. Moreover, the booking rate for MICE tourism at Al Bustan Palace Hotel reached 30%. In 2024, 3- to 5-star hotels in Oman recorded a 6.2% increase in revenues, reaching RO

		243.356 million, indicating a positive trend in the hospitality sector.
4	How does OCB support hotels in enhancing their visibility as central conference venues?	The JW Marriott Hotel Muscat, the Al Bustan Palace Hotel, and the Shangri-La Hotel all acknowledge the important role played by the OCB(OCB) in promoting hotels as central conference destinations. While both the JW Marriott Muscat and the Shangri-La Hotel highlight OCB's support in including hotels in official destination guides and organizing familiarization trips for international planners, which helps attract international events and enhances destination marketing. On the other hand, the Al Bustan Palace Hotel emphasizes a more personal partnership with OCB, noting weekly meetings and their support in exploring new markets and addressing challenges. They also mention that OCB selects hotels based on the specific needs of each event, ensuring the right alignment with the type of event.
5	What are the main challenges hotels face in hosting large conferences in Oman?	Key challenges include limited flight connectivity, visa processing times, Infrastructure, and seasonal capacity constraints. Additionally, logistical support for large-scale exhibitions is still evolving, requiring further development to meet international standards.
6	How competitive is Oman compared to other MICE destinations in the region when it comes to infrastructure and services?	Oman offers an exceptional natural beauty and high-quality hospitality services. However, it still lags behind cities like Dubai or Doha in terms of large infrastructure and recognition of established brands in the field of MICE. The country needs to improve transportation by providing luxury buses.
7	In other countries, hotels support the MICE events through sponsorships and services. How do you support OCB during International events?	They engage with OCB by providing accommodation packages, hosting networking events, and offering sponsored stays for key buyers and media representatives during international exhibitions and forums.
8	Are there specific targeted markets for international conferences that require more follow-up from the Oman Conference Bureau?	Yes, markets such as Germany and the United Kingdom, as well as regional hubs like Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates, demonstrate strong potential, but they require further effective engagement and follow-up to convert interest into confirmed events. Additionally, there should be a focus on Emerging Markets in addition to the possibility of adding the Asian market.
9	What do you think are the gaps between stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a consistently preferred destination for MICE?	Lack of alignment between the expectations of the private sector and the timelines of the public sector. More organized communications and shared performance indicators among tourism stakeholders can help bridge this gap. Additionally, the lack of awareness regarding the beauty of Oman and its hotels, compared to the Gulf countries, which are seen as more open, makes Oman a hidden gem.
10	Do you think the Oman Conference Bureau is doing enough in terms of providing logistical and promotional support for tourists attending conferences, and what suggestions do you have for improving that?	OCB is performing commendable work; there is room for improvement in the digital presence, follow-up after directives, and the logistical coordination of events. It would be beneficial to have a centralized platform for exhibitions and conferences, along with stronger on-ground support during the events. If they could slightly open the country and allow tourism to utilize nightlife as well, while providing transportation and increasing investments.
11	What kind of financial or operational incentives do you think the Oman Conference Bureau should implement to help	The subsidies for site rentals, joint marketing grants, and the streamlined visa processing for delegates will significantly enhance Oman's appeal as a destination for business conferences. Therefore, it is necessary for them to

	hotels attract more international conferences?	improve the incentive plan slightly, as what is happening is that we are receiving numerous inquiries and losing them on the market because the OCB does not provide sufficient support. Perhaps for each booking, they need to be incentivized as soon as they arrive in the country, as they tend to spend money.
12	In your opinion, to what extent should hotels prioritize the future strategic agenda of the Oman Conference Bureau?	Hotels must closely align with the vision of OCB to ensure coordination. Prioritizing joint bids, coordinated promotions, and unified branding will help Oman collectively secure larger and more prestigious events. OCB needs to undertake significant work if it wishes to attract the MICE sector to the country, and they must start by engaging with all stakeholders. When saying everyone, that means the ROP must be involved, the visa department, and migration. Muscat Airport should be engaged, and all parties must cooperate. They need to communicate with one another and unite towards a common goal. This is the way they want to move forward as a future strategy, in collaboration with the hotels.
13	What different ways can you collaborate and support MICE tourism in Oman	They can offer competitive MICE packages, engage in destination promotion, share market information with OCB, and host educational workshops or joint site visits for potential buyers.
14	What best practices do you think you can replicate that are already being practiced abroad and can be applied in Oman?	Integrated digital bidding platforms, incentive programs for repeat clients in the conference and exhibition sector, and the establishment of a MICE ambassador program are considered successful practices in countries such as Singapore and Germany, which the Sultanate of Oman can adopt. Additionally, promoting the country using influencers who are relevant to Oman or are loved by the people, similar to how Dubai promoted Yas Island through actor Shah Rukh Khan.

Table 3. MICE organizer

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How beneficial is OCB in assisting international conference organizers in event management?	Despite the significant efforts of OCB, Oman still has much to do to attract more international events, due to competition from established markets such as Dubai. International organizers do not yet perceive Oman as a highly profitable market.
2	What usual challenges do you face when organizing events in Oman, and how does OCB help resolve them?	The experience of working with venues in Oman is completely different compared to working with venues in the UAE; the service provided still lacks certain aspects. The issue with venues is that there is only one large venue, which is the OCEC, creating a monopoly. Organizers have no alternative options. Hotels suffer from a lack of space and parking for large events. OCB can assist by offering more incentives and promoting Oman as a destination more effectively.
3	What promotion strategies has the OCB employed to position Oman as a destination for MICE, and how successful have they been?	OCB's participation in events such as IMEX is beneficial, but it requires greater internal promotion within Oman itself.

4	Are there enough diverse large venues in Oman to host international events? How do the venue costs and accessibility in Oman compare to other regional conference centres like Dubai and Doha?	There is only one option for large venues in Oman - OCEC. The costs for facilities in Oman are similar to those of other regional convention centers, but the expenses are high compared to the service, which is not on par with the facilities in the Gulf Cooperation Council countries that provide multiple options. In comparison to cities like Dubai or Doha, Oman is limited in this aspect.
5	What gaps exist among stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a well-known choice for exhibitions and meetings?	There are restrictions on visas and challenges with transportation. Countries like Dubai have metro systems and easier transportation to and from venues. Oman needs to be more flexible and also attract more foreign investments, and enhance its economy to support the growth of business conferences.
6	6. Do you think that the Oman Conference Bureau genuinely supports the logistics of international events, given all the troubles related to visas, permits, and various modes of transportation?	There are restrictions related to visas and permits. OCB provides some logistical support, but the process of obtaining a visa is not easy, and the infrastructure needs improvement.
7	What types of partnerships/incentives could be offered to attract more global event organizers to choose Oman as their preferred conference destination?	If a foreign organizer wants to hold an event in Oman, they need a local partner. There should be fewer restrictions and more flexibility in the visa process, allowing more nationalities to come. Services also need to be improved. For instance, Wi-Fi in venues should be more reliable during big events because it often goes down at OCEC.
8	What kind of policy changes or infrastructure improvements could make Oman a more competitive destination for conferences and exhibitions?	The government needs to work on improving the infrastructure, specifically the transportation system.
9	Are you aware of the marketing and promotion that the OCB is doing abroad, and do you have any suggestions for improvement?	No

Table 4. Convention and Exhibition Centre

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How beneficial is OCB in assisting international conference organizers in event management?	OCB assists us by bidding for international events, supporting us with promotional materials, and facilitating the events.
2	What usual challenges do you face when organizing events in Oman, and how does OCB help resolve them?	Accessibility of flights, as most visitors to Oman transit through other countries. The Oman Aviation Committee (OAC) can assist by enhancing direct flight connections and infrastructure in Oman, particularly in hotels and venues, which can be improved to accommodate large events.
3	What promotion strategies has the OCB employed to position Oman as a destination for MICE, and how successful have they been?	OCB participants in ATM, IMEX, and IBTM. They promote Oman as the 'hidden gem of the Arabian Peninsula. Many people remain unaware of OCB's existence, as they do not focus much on internal promotion; rather, they market Oman abroad.
4	Are there enough diverse large venues in Oman to host international events? How do the venue costs and accessibility in Oman compare to other regional conference centres like Dubai and Doha?	OCEC is one of the largest venues in Oman, but there are limited options beyond that. Venue costs in Oman are competitive, and accessibility from OCEC to hotels and the airport is good.

5	What gaps exist among stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a well-known choice for exhibitions and meetings?	OCEC and OCB work closely together. There are still some areas that require further coordination among stakeholders. Oman remains an emerging market, and it will take time to build a more efficient system.
6	6. Do you think that the Oman Conference Bureau genuinely supports the logistics of international events, given all the troubles related to visas, permits, and various modes of transportation?	OCB performs excellently in logistics management, including visa and permit assistance and transportation. However, there could be further improvements, particularly in reducing the time taken to process permits and ensuring the smoothness of logistics during events.
7	What types of partnerships/incentives could be offered to attract more global event organizers to choose Oman as their preferred conference destination?	Incentives such as discounts on venue rentals, enhanced hotel amenities, and reduced costs for international visitors will be beneficial. The local market requires more facilities and hotel options to accommodate large events and an increase in the number of international delegates.
8	What kind of policy changes or infrastructure improvements could make Oman a more competitive destination for conferences and exhibitions?	No clue
9	Are you aware of the marketing and promotion that the OCB is doing abroad, and do you have any suggestions for improvement?	Yes, particularly in international exhibitions. They could increase their efforts to engage directly with international associations and enhance the visibility of Oman. More digital marketing would also assist in reaching a global audience.

Table 5. Telecommunications Industry

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How beneficial is OCB in assisting international conference organizers in event management?	OCB is effective, but it lacks the necessary resources to play a larger role in promoting Oman as a destination. The group needs to be larger to effectively support all sectors, especially for various industries such as technology.
2	What usual challenges do you face when organizing events in Oman, and how does OCB help resolve them?	They are helpful, but they need people with even greater expertise in various areas of event management. To attract more events to Oman, they should play a more advisory role in this regard.
3	What promotion strategies has the OCB employed to position Oman as a destination for MICE, and how successful have they been?	OCB is doing an excellent job in promoting Oman through the Ministry of Heritage and Tourism. OCB can enhance its efforts to market Oman as a tourist destination, as well as for MICE
4	Are there enough diverse large venues in Oman to host international events? How do the venue costs and accessibility in Oman compare to other regional conference centres like Dubai and Doha?	There is only one main venue, which is OCEC, considered excellent and highly praised by international visitors. However, Oman lacks large venues in the other governorates, making it less competitive compared to cities like Dubai or Doha. OCEC boasts outstanding facilities, but it is the only primary venue, with limited options.
5	What gaps exist among stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a well-known choice for exhibitions and meetings?	One of the gaps is the lack of promotion for Oman. Countries like Saudi Arabia and Dubai have made significant strides in promoting themselves, while Oman needs more flexibility in its investment policies and to improve communication with international stakeholders.
6	6. Do you think that the Oman Conference Bureau genuinely supports the logistics of international events, given all the troubles related	OCB assists in providing information regarding visas, transportation, and logistics; however, they require a more comprehensive team. There should be separate teams dedicated to visas, logistics, and promotion to facilitate a smoother process.

	to visas, permits, and various modes of transportation?	
7	What types of partnerships/incentives could be offered to attract more global event organizers to choose Oman as their preferred conference destination?	OCB should work on developing more facilities, especially around the conference center. The area is isolated and lacks nearby hotels, restaurants, and recreational activities. Further development in that area is needed. Additionally, more flexible marketing strategies to promote tourism in Oman would be beneficial in attracting more events.
8	What kind of policy changes or infrastructure improvements could make Oman a more competitive destination for conferences and exhibitions?	One of the main areas that requires improvement is the communication of airlines. Although Oman is close to Dubai, it needs its own local hub to enhance international communications. Furthermore, additional transportation options, such as a metro system, should be developed to improve access to events.
9	Are you aware of the marketing and promotion that the OCB is doing abroad, and do you have any suggestions for improvement?	I did not know much about what OCB does until I worked closely with them. They are doing great work, but they are overwhelmed and need additional people to work with them. I believe they could enhance their efforts in social media marketing, as it is an easier way to reach a wider audience. Furthermore, OCB should promote more local event organizers and the capacity of facilities in Oman.

Table 6. Sports Event Organizer

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How beneficial is OCB in assisting international conference organizers in event management?	OCB is an active institution, and they were cooperative with us during the visa application process and other services when welcoming players for events we organize.
2	What usual challenges do you face when organizing events in Oman, and how does OCB help resolve them?	The office is considered new, and they are trying their best, especially abroad, but they need to do more work internally. They require a more modern electronic system for reservations and travel agencies, particularly regarding visa bookings and other issues, as we faced a problem when we collaborated with Visit Oman, which is under the office's supervision. When we brought a large number of players, there were significant technical issues that prevented the completion of payment, even though the amount had already been paid, resulting in delays in visa processing and some players' arrival.
3	What promotion strategies has the OCB employed to position Oman as a destination for MICE, and how successful have they been?	Strengthening relationships with stakeholders is essential; however, OCB should take a more active role in coordinating events, whether it is booking or facilitating access.
4	Are there enough diverse large venues in Oman to host international events? How do the venue costs and accessibility in Oman compare to other regional conference centres like Dubai and Doha?	The OCEC is useful, but demand often exceeds capacity. When we organized an event during the season in December, we successfully hosted thousands of players, and the remaining numbers were distributed to various hotels, which were fully booked for 10 days. We need multipurpose halls that can accommodate a very large number of people. We can utilize the environment and work in it as a venue, as we did in Nizwa.
5	What gaps exist among stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a well-known choice for exhibitions and meetings?	Centralization is an issue that still exists, and it requires engagement with numerous institutions, governors' offices, and ministries to implement a specific activity. The gap must be closed to facilitate the execution of conferences, and there should be a stronger relationship among the stakeholders involved. We need better infrastructure. We also require greater media coverage from OCB.

6	6. Do you think that the Oman Conference Bureau genuinely supports the logistics of international events, given all the troubles related to visas, permits, and various modes of transportation?	We need to include the specialization of crowd management in the colleges.
7	What types of partnerships/incentives could be offered to attract more global event organizers to choose Oman as their preferred conference destination?	We need better transportation and support services for events so that we can keep pace with global standards.
8	What kind of policy changes or infrastructure improvements could make Oman a more competitive destination for conferences and exhibitions?	Mention earlier
9	Are you aware of the marketing and promotion that the OCB is doing abroad, and do you have any suggestions for improvement?	Not really

Table 7. Medical Association

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	How beneficial is OCB in assisting international conference organizers in event management?	An annual meeting for the association and its 48 members, which has extended over five years, aims to share ideas and discuss upcoming conferences. During these meetings, the OCB works to meet the association's needs and discuss its demands.
2	What usual challenges do you face when organizing events in Oman, and how does OCB help resolve them?	Financial support, providing halls, hotels, transportation, and airfare costs the association a lot. The support from OCB has certain conditions depending on the size of the conference and the image of authority, how it will be shaped, and how beneficial it will be for the authority. There are also issues related to obtaining visas.
3	What promotion strategies has the OCB employed to position Oman as a destination for MICE, and how successful have they been?	No clue
4	Are there enough diverse large venues in Oman to host international events? How do the venue costs and accessibility in Oman compare to other regional conference centres like Dubai and Doha?	The high cost of the OCEC and the lack of supportive services for the conference.
5	What gaps exist among stakeholders in terms of communication and collaboration that make Oman not a well-known choice for exhibitions and meetings?	The gap is that we are under the Ministry of Social Development, which has specific and strict conditions for organizing international conferences. Approvals and licenses must be obtained three months before the conference, which poses obstacles. The numerous conditions and approvals need to be simplified. There should be a communication link between the Ministry of Tourism and the Ministry of Social Development to facilitate the establishment of conferences.
6	6. Do you think that the Oman Conference Bureau genuinely supports the logistics of international events, given all the troubles related	They are very cooperative; the numerous conditions limit the organization of conferences in terms of the number of attendees. We hope for more facilitation.

	to visas, permits, and various modes of transportation?	
7	What types of partnerships/incentives could be offered to attract more global event organizers to choose Oman as their preferred conference destination?	We held 20 medical conferences last year, and greater attention should be directed towards this aspect.
8	What kind of policy changes or infrastructure improvements could make Oman a more competitive destination for conferences and exhibitions?	Greater attention should be paid to infrastructure and roads, and efforts should be made to promote the country more extensively, as conference visitors are always surprised upon arriving in the country and witnessing its beauty.
9	Are you aware of the marketing and promotion that the OCB is doing abroad, and do you have any suggestions for improvement?	No

Table 8. Government and Tourism Authorities OCB

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	What key strategies is OCB currently using in promoting Oman as a MICE destination?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sales calls targeting (International MICE DMCS - MICE houses- corporate companies in different sectors - PCOs - associations) • roadshows jointly with local stakeholders • participation in the MICE trade shows and events • attracting MICE educational trips to Oman for potential companies and associations • digital and printed marketing • important events sponsorships • attracting b2b events to Oman
2	How do you collaborate with organizations like ICCA to jointly promote Oman in larger global markets?	The OCB collaborates with several international associations, such as IA, Site, and PCMA. These collaborations encompass education, marketing, and business generation. For instance, cooperation with IA includes participation in international events, such as their global conference, where various destinations and organizations provide updates on the sector. The partnership with Site involves offering recognized educational programs, such as the CIS (Certified Incentive Specialist) program, which provides a fundamental understanding of the MICE sector and rewards participants with globally acknowledged certificates. Additionally, the Authority collaborates with hotel chains like IHG, leveraging their international offices and data to promote Oman as a MICE destination, ensuring mutual benefits by attracting corporate clients. Similar partnerships are forged with local companies that manage destinations with international branches to market Oman using their customer data.
3	Name the membership you have in international bodies representing MICE?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The International Congress and Convention Association (ICCA) - The Society for Incentive Travel Excellence (SITE) - Professional Convention Management Association (PCMA) - The International Association of Professional Congress Organizers (IAPCO) *not a membership but collaboration *
4	What are the main challenges facing OCB in seeking to attract foreign conference organizers?	The challenges relate to several aspects. Firstly, Oman has a smaller business volume compared to other destinations, making it less attractive for international conference organizers to establish offices. For instance, while destinations like Dubai or Singapore host over 50 conferences annually, Oman hosts

		about 5 to 6 conferences. Secondly, there is competition from other destinations that offer greater financial incentives to attract conferences. For example, some destinations extend multiple offers for a single conference, thereby increasing their chances of winning. Locally, the strength and interest of associations are also crucial. If local authorities, such as the Ministry of Health, are not involved or interested in a conference (for instance, a medical conference), it becomes challenging to compete for it.
5	What has the growth trend of conference tourism in Oman been over the past five years, and what are the targets for the next five years?	Yes, there are plans to increase financial support; however, currently, assistance is provided on a case-by-case basis. Each conference and event is evaluated based on its economic impact, and we strive to increase the budget and the number of activities each year.
6	How does OCB engage with private sector stakeholders (hotels and event organizers) to further improve the overall conference and exhibition ecosystem within Oman?	OCB engages with stakeholders through regular updates, quarterly meetings, and educational programs. We focus on both conferences and incentives, where we provide at least two educational programs annually and host gatherings such as breakfasts with local associations. Additionally, we are evaluating new markets, such as China, and collaborating with stakeholders to assess their readiness.
7	What are the main investments in the infrastructure dedicated to building conference and exhibition tourism in Oman?	Investments are divided into hard investments (infrastructure, hotels, and increasing venue capacities) and soft investments (developing local DMCs, PCOs, and event organizers). New hotels, such as Indigo in Oman and areas like Jabal Akhdar, support the conference and events sector. There are also plans for further expansion in hotels and venues. Additionally, local DMC companies, such as Magic Arabia with its new conference and exhibition-focused brand 'Spice', are encouraged to grow and enhance local and international conference operations.
8	How does OCB assess the success of its conference tourism strategies? And which important performance indicators (KPIs) have been defined?	Success is evaluated through key performance indicators, with a primary focus on the number of conferences, meetings, and targeted incentive groups each year. The key performance targets for this year have been nearly achieved, with a 90% success rate in the first two quarters. Success is also measured by economic impact, an increase in tourist numbers, and compliance with the Oman 2040 Vision. Key performance indicators are reviewed annually to assess performance.
9	Which promising markets is OCB envisioning to target for business tourism?	The OCB targets markets based on specialization rather than specific regions. For conferences, they focus on associations related to sectors, such as medical associations. For incentives and meetings, they are targeting the Asian market, particularly China, which is showing positive interest. This year, the Russian market is also being explored. The Asian market is considered highly promising for business tourism in Oman.
10	What are the major policy changes under consideration that will facilitate the holding of an international conference in Oman?	The Oman Conference Office is exploring several major political changes, including the allocation of dedicated staff for research purposes and bidding operations. This will require collaboration with relevant authorities such as the Ministry of Technology or the Ministry of Sports, depending on the conference sector. They are also working to achieve synergy with governmental bodies, such as Oman Airports and Visit Oman, to attract more business travellers. Additionally, the implementation of an ambassador program is being considered, where selected ambassadors from key sectors such as medical, technology, oil and gas, and transportation will assist in bidding processes, lobbying, and promoting conferences. Furthermore, efforts are being made to raise awareness about the importance

		of meetings and tourism incentives and to secure funding, particularly for incentives and support.
11	What challenges does OCB face from stakeholders that limit its performance in terms of winning international bids for MICE?	The challenges facing the OCB include a lack of coordination among the stakeholders, outdated policies, low commitment from local authorities, and weak participation from stakeholders like hotels and airlines. There's a need to improve collaboration, increase flight options, and offer competitive prices for conferences.
12	What structural challenges are faced by OCB that limit its performance in terms of winning international bids for MICE?	Oman's conference office faces structural challenges due to its limited size in terms of staff and budget. Compared to successful destinations, their conference office operates with fewer staff and a smaller budget. To improve the situation, increasing the number of professional and educated staff within the office, as well as boosting its budget, will help expand its scope. This would allow Oman to attract more conferences and groups interested in meetings and incentives, and it would enhance efforts in exhibitions, which is an area currently suffering from a lack of development due to staff constraints. A larger team and increased resources would provide greater capacity to effectively promote Oman as a business conference destination.

Table 9. Oman Vision 2040

#	Interview Questions	Responses
1	What is your role in supporting international events in Oman?	The government's role is crucial in enhancing tourism by supporting international events to diversify the economy. This includes investment in world-class facilities like the Oman Convention and Exhibition Center, Royal Opera House, and cultural projects like the Oman Museum and Oman Cultural Complex. The Ministry of Heritage and Tourism promotes Oman through initiatives like Oman Vision 2040, which facilitates event hosting and encourages investment.
2	What has the growth trend of conference tourism in Oman been over the past five years, and what are the targets for the next five years?	The conference tourism sector in Oman has witnessed significant growth, driven by strategic investments in infrastructure. This growth has been supported by government backing and alignment with Oman Vision 2040. This sector, which had a value ranging from 700 to 800 million dollars in 2018, aims to attract 17 international conferences by 2024, with a target of reaching 35 annual conferences by 2030. Furthermore, the number of meetings and incentive groups is expected to reach 100 annually by 2030.
3	What has the growth trend of conference tourism in Oman been over the past five years, and what are the targets for the next five years?	The ministry focuses on expanding the tourism infrastructure, particularly through the construction of new high-quality hotels and event facilities to accommodate future international events. Additionally, efforts will be made to enhance Oman's role as a key location for international conferences and exhibitions.
4	What has the growth trend of conference tourism in Oman been over the past five years, and what are the targets for the next five years?	Oman has made significant investments in infrastructure, including modern airports, roads, and luxury hotels, to support international events. The Oman Convention and Exhibition Centre (OCEC) is a key venue for large-scale events, and further development is planned around the conference center and other tourist facilities. Sustainable practices will be integrated into the meetings, incentives, and exhibitions industry, with an emphasis on environmentally friendly events and reducing the carbon footprint.

Summary of Findings

Interviews across the hospitality sector, event organizers, OCEC representatives, government entities, and professional associations highlighted the Oman Convention Bureau's (OCB) central role in promoting Oman as a MICE destination. Hotels such as JW Marriott, Al Bustan Palace, and Shangri-La reported close collaboration with OCB through joint bids, international exhibitions (IMEX, ATM), co-branding, and familiarization trips. These efforts improved visibility and generated between 20–53% of their MICE-related occupancy, with one hotel noting a 6.2% revenue increase. Stakeholders acknowledged Oman's cultural appeal, natural beauty, and quality hospitality but cited major challenges, including limited flight connectivity, visa delays, seasonal capacity constraints, and evolving infrastructure. Comparisons with Dubai and Doha underscored Oman's weaker global brand recognition and transportation facilities.

Event organizers and private companies appreciated OCB's logistical support, visa facilitation, and promotional campaigns abroad, yet many noted limited internal promotion, under-resourcing, and a heavy dependence on the Oman Convention and Exhibition Centre (OCEC). This concentration created monopolistic challenges, while hotels lacked sufficient space and parking for large events. Stakeholders called for stronger digital platforms, more coordinated stakeholder engagement, streamlined visa processes, subsidies for site rentals, and incentives for international delegates. Technical issues, such as disrupted Wi-Fi and payment glitches, were also reported during events. Respondents emphasized the need for improved transportation networks, diversified venues beyond Muscat, and better alignment between public and private sectors.

Government representatives and associations confirmed OCB's alignment with Oman Vision 2040, citing its success in generating USD 700–800 million in 2018 and aiming to host 35 international conferences and 100 incentive groups annually by 2030. While OCB has achieved 90% of its key performance indicators and received recognition for international trade show participation and global partnerships (ICCA, SITE, PCMA), gaps remain in staffing, budget, and stakeholder communication. Suggested improvements included stronger digital presence, repeat client incentives, ambassador programs, joint promotions with airlines and hotels, and policy simplification. Overall, while stakeholders acknowledged OCB's pivotal role in positioning Oman as a 'hidden gem' in the MICE market, they emphasized that enhanced resources, collaboration, and infrastructure are critical for the country to compete effectively with established regional hubs.

Conclusion

The Oman Convention Bureau (OCB) operates under a hybrid model, embedded within the Ministry of Heritage and Tourism and largely dependent on government funding and strategic directives. While OCB has made commendable strides through collaborations with global organizations such as ICCA, SITE, and PCMA—moving towards a knowledge-driven model similar to Singapore—its operational capacity remains constrained. Unlike regional leaders such as the UAE or Singapore, OCB lacks full autonomy, scalability, and robust cross-sector integration, limiting its ability to maximize Oman's potential in the highly competitive MICE market.

Despite being widely recognized as a key enabler of MICE tourism, OCB's impact is hindered by structural limitations, insufficient resources, and gaps in inter-agency coordination. The findings further underscore the importance of stakeholder collaboration, particularly with private sector players. However, many private stakeholders perceive a lack of cohesive government support and coordinated initiatives, leaving Oman at a competitive disadvantage compared to regional peers with more mature ecosystems.

To realize Oman Vision 2040 goals and strengthen its position as a distinctive MICE destination, OCB must evolve into a more independent and resource-equipped institution. This requires deeper collaboration between government and private stakeholders, greater investment in infrastructure and digital systems, and the establishment of a more agile, market-driven operating model. Only through such structural and strategic reforms can Oman unlock the full potential of its convention and tourism sector and position itself as a sustainable, competitive, and innovative MICE hub in the region.

Recommendations

To strengthen Oman's position as a competitive MICE destination and to align with Oman Vision 2040, the following recommendations are proposed:

- **Enhance Stakeholder Coordination**
 - Establish structured communication platforms such as quarterly or biannual stakeholder forums, involving airlines, hotels, ministries, and OCB.
 - Develop clear MICE Partnership Agreements (MPAs) that define roles, responsibilities, and performance metrics linked to Vision 2040 targets.
 - Foster joint bids and unified branding campaigns to project Oman as a cohesive destination.
- **Strengthen Incentives and Recognition**
 - Introduce financial incentives such as venue rental subsidies, visa facilitation, and marketing grants to attract repeat and large-scale conferences.
 - Recognize and reward stakeholder contributions through newsletters, awards, and public acknowledgment of successful collaborations.
 - Provide tailored packages for high-value clients, including repeat incentives for associations and international organizers.
- **Build Capacity and Professional Expertise**
 - Expand OCB's staff and recruit professionals with event management expertise to enhance operational delivery.
 - Invest in training programs for local talent, including specialized areas such as crowd management, logistics, and digital marketing.
 - Consider transitioning OCB into a semi-autonomous or independent bureau to increase flexibility and agility, drawing on best practices from global peers.
- **Streamline Processes and Leverage Technology**
 - Simplify bureaucratic procedures for visas, permits, and approvals to minimize delays for organizers and participants.
 - Develop an integrated digital platform for event bidding, stakeholder communication, and performance monitoring, enabling transparent sharing of leads and opportunities.
 - Use real-time data analytics to evaluate economic impact and track progress against strategic goals.
- **Expand Digital Presence and Marketing**
 - Strengthen OCB's global digital presence through targeted campaigns, influencer engagement, and continuous communication with event planners.
 - Launch domestic awareness campaigns to improve recognition of OCB's role among local stakeholders.
 - Integrate CRM systems and digital bidding tools to facilitate stronger international engagement.
- **Focus on Niche and Aligned Events**
 - Position Oman as a destination for high-value, smaller-scale conferences in sectors aligned with Vision 2040, such as sustainability, healthcare, energy, technology, and sports.
 - Leverage Oman's cultural heritage and natural beauty to differentiate its MICE offering from high-volume destinations like Dubai or Doha.
 - Develop ambassador programs to engage academics, industry leaders, and professional associations in attracting global events.
- **Invest in Infrastructure and Connectivity**
 - Improve international flight connectivity and explore the development of a regional airline hub to enhance accessibility.
 - Invest in transport networks such as luxury buses and consider long-term solutions like metro systems to facilitate venue access.
 - Expand venue capacity beyond Muscat to other governorates and develop supporting hospitality infrastructure near major event sites.

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